
N-LIST: A Resource for Innovative Learning and Research

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Abstract:

The paper succinctly describes the programmes and services of INFLIBNET, N-LIST E-Consortium, membership of libraries, use of resource, and devices used by users to search information from N-LIST. A study was conducted by virtually observing 17 college libraries in Chandrapur district affiliated with Gondwana University. It was found that 59% (10) of libraries have the e-N-List Consortium available. 72% of students, 68% of academics, 100% of researchers, and 80% of the overall users used N-List. Overall, an average of 50% of users used computers, 28% laptops, and 90% mobile devices to search for information from the N-List Consortium. Mobile has been used more than any other tool to search for information in the NLIST resource. The information available in these resources can be viewed anywhere, around the clock which save time, money and energy. The Government of India recently launched the “One Nation One Subscription Scheme” on January 1, 2025, and its coordinator is Infflibnet. Private college libraries in tribal, backward and hilly areas will be able to provide services more efficiently if they are given some concession in subscription rates. So it is worth recommending. This study found that N-List was a useful resource of information for users for innovative learning and research.

Keywords: INFLIBNET, N-LIST E- Consortium, Membership, Use of N-LIST, Devices

Introduction:

The students are presently studying in virtual classrooms due to technological innovations in the education sector. Information is desperately needed for this innovative change. In the changing scenario, conventional sources of information have been replaced by non-conventional methods. Digital information sources have brought about a radical change in this. Considering current and future information needs, organizations providing information in digital form have emerged globally, and India is no exception. The Indian Information Library Network (INFLIBNET), Gandhinagar, Gujarat, and the National Digital Library of India

(NDLI), IIT, Kharagpur, W.B., are functioning in India in the interest of users. College libraries are also working to provide information services to users through the N-LIST consortium resources with the help of Infflibnet.

Need of the Study:

The need for this study arose as NLIST under Infflibnet is a popular resource for users to access information for innovative education and research through journals and books. The information available in these resources can be viewed anywhere, around the clock.

Scope of the Study and Methodology:

A mini sample survey was conducted on the availability of the N-LIST Consortium in the libraries of 17 Arts, Commerce and Science colleges in Chandrapur district affiliated with Gondwana University, Virtual and online questionnaires, as well as a website, were used for data collection

Objectives of the Study:

1. Accessing programme and services, e-resources from INFLIBNET's website
2. To know information about N-LIST e-Consortium
3. Surveying the availability of N-LIST e-resources in college libraries
4. To know the information about the usage of N-List e-resources by the users
5. Exploring the tools used by users regarding the use of N-List e-resources
6. To see NLIST as an important resource for users for innovative learning and research

INFLIBNET -Information and Library Network Centre:

The Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre at Gandhinagar, Gujarat is an autonomous Inter-University Centre (IUC) of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi (Ministry of Education, Government of India). It is a major national programme that the UGC launched on 27 February 1991 as a project under IUCAA. On 16 May 1996, it became an independent Inter-University Centre. It is involved in modernizing university libraries in India by using cutting-edge technology for optimal use of

information. It will be a key vehicle for promoting scholarly dialogue among academics and researchers in India.

1. Programmes and services of the Centre:

Technology is a driving force in the modern education system. The Centre has undertaken several initiatives to benefit the educational community in India. These initiatives are categorized into various phenomenons under programs and services. From a study perspective, all events are presented under the heading of a review of research.

2. Programs and services of INFLIBNET

- .Library Automation
- E-Consortium
- Open Access Initiative
- Scholarly Network
- E-Content Development and Services

3. N-LIST- National Library and Information Services Infrastructure:

The Project entitled "National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)", graduated as a regular scheme of UGC under UGC-

INFONET Digital Library Consortium as college component is merged into e-ShodhSindhu: Consortia for Higher Education E-Resources. The N-LIST provides access to 6,000+ journals, 1,64,300+ e-Books under N-LIST and 6,00,000 e-Books through NDL to all Govt., Govt.-aided as well as non-aided colleges through a proxy server / shibboleth. All colleges covered under Sections 12(B) and 2(f) of the UGC Act. Non-Aided colleges (except Agriculture, Engineering, Management, Medical, Pharmacy, Dentistry and Nursing) are eligible to join this programme. Annual membership fee for registered colleges Rs. 5900 and non-granted Rs. 35400.

Table 1: Member of N-List College Libraries

Services	N-LIST-Membership of Libraries		
	Total Libraries	N-LIST Member	Percentage %
E-Consortium			
N-LIST	17	10	59

Source: Virtual survey and website

Fig: 1

Table 1 shows that the data of the members of Inlibnet, an N-list of 17 arts, commerce and science college libraries in Chandrapur district affiliated with

Gondwana University, Gadchiroli, was collected virtually. It was found that 10 (59%) college libraries registered for membership in the N-List

Table 5.3.2: Use of N-LIST by the users

Services	Students			Academicians			Researchers			Average %
	Total	Use	%	Total	Use	%	Total	Use	%	
E-Consortium										
N-LIST	120	86	72	90	61	68	25	25	100	80 %

Source: Virtual survey and website

Fig: 2.1

Table 2 shows that 72% of students, 68% of academicians, and 100% of researchers used N-LIST to search journal

articles. Overall 80 % users of the 10 college libraries of Arts, Commerce and Science, Chandrapur district, affiliated to Gondwana

University, Gadchiroli were used to search the journals from the E-Consortium. It was found that users from the remaining 7

colleges were accessing information from the respective libraries where this service was available.

Table 3: Devices used by the users

Medium used to view N-LIST	Students			Academicians			Researchers			Average
	Total	Use	%	Total	Use	%	Total	Use	%	% P
Computer	120	51	42	90	50	55	25	13	52	50
Laptop	120	15	12	90	24	27	25	11	44	28
Mobile	120	110	92	90	70	78	25	25	100	90

Source: Virtual survey and website

Fig: 3.3

Table 3 shows that 42% of students, 55% of academics and 52% of researchers used computer media to search for information from the N-list. It was found that, 12% of students, 27% of academics and 44% of researchers using laptops. 92% of students, 78% of academics and 100% of researchers used mobile devices to search for information. Overall, an average of 50% of users used computers, 28% laptops, and 90% mobile devices to search for information from the N-List Consortium. This shows that mobile devices are increasingly being used to search for information. Therefore, mobile has become a popular medium.

Findings and Recommendations:

It was found that N-LIST is the E-Consortium INFLIBNET service and merged into e-ShodhSindhu: and providing e-journals and e-books to their subscribers.

A mini survey was conducted on the availability of the N-LIST Consortium in the libraries of 17 Arts, Commerce and Science colleges in Chandrapur district affiliated with Gondwana University, Gadchiroli. Of these, 10 (59%) libraries were found to have the E-NLIST Consortium available. 72% of students, 68% of academics, 100% of researchers, and 80% of the overall users used N-List to search for e-journal articles and books. Those who do not have this system are using other college libraries to search for information from N-LIST. Overall, an average of 50% of users used computers, 28% laptops, and 90% mobile devices to search for information from the N-List Consortium. Being a rural, tribal and backward-class area, it is economically weak. Therefore, it was found that students cannot afford laptops and hence their usage is low. Mobiles were found to be popular for information seeking as they are convenient

to use and around the clock. Studies have shown that Enlisting is being used more and more.

The N-List was a useful resource for users in education, research, and development. Like the subsidized ones, private college libraries require a modest subscription. It also affected the users of private college libraries.

The Government of India recently launched the One Nation One Membership Scheme on January 1, 2025, and its coordinator is Inflibnet. Private college libraries in tribal, backward and hilly areas will be able to provide services more efficiently if they are given some concession

in subscription rates. So it is worth recommending.

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